

Narratives of religious dissidence in medieval inquisition records: computing the representation and sequencing of crimes in Peter Seila's register of sentences (1241–2)

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Introduction

Medieval inquisition trial records, produced by ecclesiastical tribunals tasked with investigating and prosecuting heresy, are among the richest sources for the social and religious history of medieval Europe. They are also fundamentally narrative documents, since (in line with usual definitions of narrative) they are characterized by the serial representation of events (Barthes, 1975; Genette, 1980; Abbott, 2020) in which suspects and witnesses participated. Yet the narrative qualities of these sources – how they represent and sequence reported dissident actions – have rarely been systematically studied across entire registers. Scholars have typically focused on exceptionally rich depositions (Zbiral and Shaw, 2022, pp.10–12), leaving aside a larger body of less striking testimonies, often formulaic in appearance, which nevertheless tell stories of religious dissidence. This paper presents the first computational analysis of narrativity across the totality of cases within a single inquisitorial register, examining how stories were constructed through the interaction of inquisitor, notary, and suspects.

Research questions and materials

We analyse Peter Seila's register of sentences (1241–2, Southern France), documenting the conviction of 650 individuals and providing summaries of guilt for 649 (Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France, MS Doat 21, fols. 185r–324r); it is the earliest inquisition register to cover hundreds of individuals. Its summaries allow comparison by gender (391 men, 258 women), by dissident ministers interacted with (359 with *heretici* only, 189 with *valdenses* only, 98 with both), and across nine regional sentencing events spanning Ascension 1241 through Lent 1242 (Duvernoy, 2001; Feuchter, 2007; Taylor, 2011).

Our investigation addresses two dimensions: (1) the representation of criminal events and states – what crimes are mentioned, how they are semantically framed, and how this varies by gender, sect, and sentencing context; and (2) the sequencing of these components – summary length and structure, the presence of sub-narratives concerning particular contact occasions, and crime ordering (the sequence in which different crimes appear within each summary). We seek to clarify the balance between preconception and exploration in Peter's inquisition, and to recover how the voices of inquisitor, deponent, and notary were interwoven.

Methods

Peter Seila's register was captured as over 10,000 data statements using the Computer-Assisted Semantic Text Modelling (CASTEMO) approach (Zbiral et al., 2022). Each verbal clause was manually transformed into a data statement, preserving exact Latin verbal semantics, actants, circumstances, and textual order. This avoided strong pre-categorization during data collection.

We classified crimes at two levels: 143 granular crime types derived inductively from the register's own lexico-semantic distinctions, and 6 broader categories (Seeing and Seeking, Information Exchange, Resource Exchange/Practical Support, Communing, Ritual, Belief). Crimes were further classified by semantic framing (expressions denoting recurrence, aggravating or alleviating circumstances, location specification) and contextual factors.

For the analysis of sequencing, we quantified summary lengths and identified sub-narratives through non-adjacent crime repetition patterns. We also developed a computational procedure measuring conformity between crime ordering in Peter's summaries and the question list in the near-contemporary *Narbonne Order of Procedure* inquisition manual (c. 1244; Sackville, 2019), validated through permutation testing against 10,000 random reorderings.

Results and discussion

The summaries are dominated by tangible events, particularly making contact and material exchange. The top 10 crime types account for 73.24% of all crimes, with *vidit* ('saw') alone representing 23.36%. This narrow vocabulary – likely reflecting inquisitorial questioning and notarial standardization rather than suspects' natural diction – underpins the register's formulaic feel.

The semantic framing of crimes reveals sophisticated patterns illuminating the summaries' multivocality. Expressions denoting recurrence (e.g., 'many times') spike for readily repeatable actions like *vidit*, suggesting efficient notarial aggregation; yet they appear independent of crime severity, indicating that recurrence expressions reflected how events were naturally reported rather than diminished investigative interest. Alleviating circumstances appear most frequently with Communing crimes (5.59%), likely reflecting inquisitorial probing of ambiguous acts: eating with ministers could suggest intimacy or happenstance. Elevated locational details around certain crimes suggest multiple influences: for housing crimes (*recepit*), the regular presence of 'in his/her house' (a detail that might be inferred from the action itself) may reflect the engrained narrative tendencies of any party – inquisitor, deponent, or notary – in situating place-bound acts.

Gender differences are nuanced rather than typecast, suggesting openness to individual experience. Male suspects were more often portrayed eating and drinking with dissident ministers, while female suspects are nearly twice as likely to have Belief crimes (44.19% vs. 24.81%). Narrative content shows stronger ties to minister type: *valdenses*-associated crimes emphasize beliefs and information exchange, while *heretici*-associated crimes feature more ritual acts.

Sequence analysis reveals evolving practices. After Ascension 1241, summaries become shorter and more organized around crime types rather than particular contact occasions: non-adjacent crime repetitions – our proxy for sub-narratives exploring individual occasions – decline dramatically, suggesting notarial refinement toward efficient, composite narratives.

Conformity analysis demonstrates a strong relationship between Peter's summaries and the *Narbonne Order* question list. The mean of the conformity index that we established for each summary is 0.78

(SD=0.25), with only 0.40% of random orderings producing higher conformity ($p < 0.004$). However, this is driven primarily by frequent crime pairs (*vidit* before *audivit*, *vidit* before *credidit*) rather than strict adherence to overall structure: for instance, many summaries begin with crimes other than *vidit* (37.75%), the simple act of seeing that is the first crime in the *Narbonne Order* sequence. The analysis suggests underlying interrogations that could be flexible and explorative; these were subsequently (if imperfectly) refined through notarial organization. While Peter probably used a question list, the link to the slightly later *Narbonne Order* is strongest in the most refined summaries, which may have influenced its compilers.

Conclusions

Peter Seila's seemingly bland summaries reveal a process balancing exploration and standardization. The underlying depositions were likely biographical in structure, exploring contact occasions in depth, but the notary increasingly organized this material around crime types, creating efficient, standardized summary narratives of descent into heresy. This standardization laid the groundwork for more perfunctory investigations suggested by the rigid *Narbonne Order* question list, which closely mirrored the language and ordering of Peter's most refined summaries.

Our methodology demonstrates the power of computational narrative analysis: it enables detection of hard-to-perceive patterns and illuminates textual and interpersonal processes shaping these documents. By analyzing narrativity systematically across entire registers rather than inferring from exceptional examples, we can understand the 'construction' of heresy as a complex multivocal process, rather than as an axiomatic presence imposed by inquisitors.

Keywords

narrative analysis, Computer-Assisted Semantic Text Modelling (CASTEMO), computational text analysis, sequence analysis, religious dissidence and repression

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